

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Visually Transparent and Scalable Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells Through Spatial Segmentation

Nuno Rodrigues¹ | José Fonseca¹ | Pedro Santos¹ | Rico Gutzler²

¹INL - International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Braga, Portugal | ²Zentrum für Sonnenenergie- und Wasserstoff-Forschung Baden-Württemberg (ZSW), Stuttgart, Germany | ³Department of Physics and Materials Science, University of Luxembourg, Belvaux, Luxembourg

Correspondence: Pedro Anacleto (pedro.anacleto@inl.int) | Sascha Sadewasser (sascha.sadewasser@inl.int)

Received: 20 February 2026 | **Revised:** 27 March 2026 | **Accepted:** 2 April 2026

Keywords: building-integrated photovoltaics | Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ | semi-transparent photovoltaics

ABSTRACT

Semi-transparent photovoltaics aim to integrate power generation into building windows without compromising visual neutrality. Yet, most approaches achieve transparency by thinning the absorber layer, which reduces efficiency and leads to transmission of tinted light. Spatial segmentation provides an alternative where transparency is set by the aperture-area ratio, while the full absorber thickness and its photovoltaic quality can be preserved. We implement this concept in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin-film solar cells using a bottom-up approach that defines sub-visible micro-stripes prior to deposition and supports the efficient use of absorber material. To demonstrate scalability, we fabricate and characterise a semi-transparent mini-module with a series interconnection along the segmented stripes. The mini-module has 40% average visible transmittance and achieves 10.9% active-area efficiency, resulting in a light-utilisation efficiency of 2.2%, while retaining a colour-neutral appearance. These results show that geometric segmentation can translate full-thickness thin-film absorbers into viable, visually non-obtrusive photovoltaic windows, offering a practical route towards high-performance building-integrated photovoltaics.

1 | Introduction

Transparent and semi-transparent photovoltaic (STPV) technologies are increasingly viewed as a key route for expanding solar deployment across the built environment [1], aiming to turn building windows into energy harvesters without compromising visual quality. Most thin-film approaches, including amorphous Si [2], CdTe [3], or Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) [4], create transparency by thinning the absorber layer from >2 μm down to 0.4 μm or below. In CIGS, absorber thinning reduces efficiency mainly due to short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) losses [5], caused by interface recombination [6], which becomes increasingly significant for thin absorber layers. Thin absorbers also introduce colour tint because the wavelength-dependent absorption results in longer wavelength light passing through while short-wavelength light is absorbed, thereby altering the transmitted colour.

Reported semi-transparent CIGS devices illustrate this trade-off with reported power conversion efficiencies (PCE) of ~6%–10% for CIGS absorbers with 200–300 nm thickness, leading to ~9% average visible transmittance (AVT) [7–9], and ~12%–13% PCE at ~500 nm absorber thickness with ~7%–8% transmittance [10, 11]. Higher transparency (25% AVT) has been demonstrated, but only at the expense of reduced efficiency (~6%) [12]. Therefore, there is a clear need for an STPV architecture that offers colour-neutral transparency without sacrificing photovoltaic performance, pointing toward strategies that maintain full absorber quality and generate transparency by patterning the device instead of thinning the absorber.

A semi-transparent CIGS mini-module has been elegantly demonstrated using laser ablation to open circular apertures through the absorber thickness, thus creating device transparency, while

Nuno Rodrigues, José Fonseca and Pedro Santos joint co-authorship.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Solar RRL* published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

retaining full absorber thickness in the active regions, providing an important benchmark [13]. In our work, device transparency is achieved through spatial segmentation, with the CIGS layer patterned into parallel micro-strips separated by transparent gaps. The transparency level is set by the aperture-area ratio (AAR), defined as the fraction of the illuminated surface that is free of absorber material, as well as the AVT of the transparent area, i.e., of glass and transparent layers above (if applicable). For a full-thickness absorber, the AAR provides a direct and geometry-controlled way to set the device's AVT. AVT represents the transmittance of the solar cell weighted by the photopic response of the human eye (details in the Supporting Information S1) [14]. The visual appearance of a segmented absorber is governed by the stripe width W and the spacing S (Figure 1A). When W lies below the visual acuity limit of the human eye ($\approx 300 \mu\text{m}$ at 1 m viewing distance), the pattern becomes effectively invisible, and the surface appears uniform and colour-neutral (Figure 1B).

Increasing the stripe coverage enhances the total photovoltaic area but reduces AAR, leading to the characteristic trade-off between transparency and PCE illustrated in Figure 1C. This simple geometric control provides a direct and tunable route to colour-neutral semi-transparency while retaining full absorber thickness. Figure 1D shows a 75%-AAR demonstrator based on metallic lines on glass.

Implementing this geometric concept in thin-film CIGS requires reliable pattern transfer, which introduces fabrication challenges at both the absorber and back-contact interfaces. Here, we

explore two photolithography approaches to create micro-stripped CIGS, as shown in Figure 2. In both approaches, photoresist micro-trenches define the stripe boundaries before deposition, enabling a bottom-up formation of the segmented CIGS absorber.

When Mo and amorphous (a-)CIGS are sputtered into the defined trenches (Figure 2A-4), the incoming materials partially coat the resist sidewalls (inset of Figure 2A-4), forming structures known as "ears" or "wing tips" (inset of Figure 2A-5), which can bridge to the solar cell top contact and create shunt pathways. Minimising this sidewall deposition is therefore essential for reliable fabrication. Two complementary mitigation strategies were explored. The first uses sodium-hypochlorite (bleach) etch, which selectively etches Mo and produces a slight lateral recess beneath the CIGS, before crystallization of the a-CIGS precursor (Figure 2A-6) [15]. This straightforward route requires only a single wet-etch step to create a small undercut that helps interrupt sidewall continuity. The second approach employs a lift-off-resist (LOR) bilayer, a conventional method for defining an undercut resist profile, that yields a tapered film geometry, enabling the a-CIGS coverage over the Mo (Figure 2B-6) [16]. Both strategies are evaluated in Section 2 for their influence on shunting behaviour, contact integrity, and overall device performance.

The bottom-up approach also offers a material-efficiency advantage: the Cu, In, Ga, Se, and Mo deposited on the photoresist are released into the lift-off solvent, allowing recovery of these elements, most importantly indium and gallium, which are critical

FIGURE 1 | Concept of spatial segmentation for semi-transparent CIGS. (A) Schematic of a micro-stripped STPV device, where stripe width W and spacing S define the AAR. (B) Visual acuity limit of the human eye (calculation in Supporting Information S2). (C) Trade-off between AAR and total-area power conversion efficiency (PCE), assuming an opaque reference device with 20% PCE. (D) Photo focused on a visual demonstrator sample with 75% aperture-area ratio (AAR) formed by narrow metallic lines on glass.

FIGURE 2 | Schematic illustration of the bottom-up approaches for forming micro-striped CIGS, shown in cross-section. A single stripe is depicted for clarity. (A) Process using Mo etching with bleach: resist-defined trenches (steps 1–3) receive sputtered Mo and a-CIGS (step 4), which produce sidewall features along the resist profile (step 5). A bleach etching introduces a slight Mo recess that disrupts this continuity (step 6). (B) Lift-off-resist (LOR) bilayer approach: the resist undercut (steps 1–4) leads to a tapered deposited film (step 5) that limits continuous sidewall formation. In both routes, the patterned a-CIGS is crystallized to form the CIGS absorber and subsequently completed with buffer and window layers (steps 7–8).

raw materials, an option not available in top-down subtractive approaches such as laser ablation or wet etching [13, 17].

While these strategies allow reliable fabrication of isolated micro-strips, larger-area devices require series-interconnected cells to enable efficient current collection [13]. In this work, we implement this principle across many micro-strips by demonstrating a $2.92 \times 2.35 \text{ cm}^2$ (total area) series-interconnected CIGS STPV mini-module achieving 40.6% visible transmittance, 10.9% active-area efficiency, and a light-utilisation efficiency of 2.2%, realised through a top-down fabrication route based on photoresist patterning and chemical etching, and we present the corresponding optical and electrical characterisation.

2 | Experimental

2.1 | Bottom-Up Fabrication of Micro-Striped STPVs

We fabricated micro-striped test structures comprising parallel CIGS stripes of 200, 300, 500, and 1000 μm width, each 6 mm long and separated by 700 μm gaps on the same substrate. These structures served as the basis for evaluating the two bottom-up patterning approaches described below.

2.1.1 | Bleach-Etch Route

A 1 mm thick soda-lime glass (SLG) was coated with a 2.2 μm thick photoresist (PR) layer (AZP 4110 Microchem, Ulm, Germany) and patterned into micro lines using a direct-write laser (DWL) (DWL 2000, Heidelberg Instruments, Heidelberg, Germany) (Figure 2A-2,3). A 500 nm Mo back-contact bilayer was DC-sputtered into the photoresist trenches (the first 100 nm at 47 W and 1.3×10^{-2} mbar, followed by 400 nm at 50 W and

6.9×10^{-3} mbar) using the home-built STAR system [18]. A $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ -thick amorphous CIGS precursor layer was deposited at room temperature by DC co-sputtering from two Cu–In–Ga targets with Cu–In–Ga compositions of 50–35–15 at% (Testbourne, at 30 W power) and 15–60–25 at% (Testbourne, at 5 W power), at a working pressure of 5.5×10^{-3} mbar, while selenium was simultaneously evaporated in a pulsed mode (Figure 2A-4). Material deposited on top of the PR was removed by lift-off in an acetone bath, followed by rinsing with isopropanol and deionised water and drying with N_2 (Figure 2A-5). Next, the patterned films were immersed in a regular household bleach (active chlorine concentration $< 5\%$) for 60 s to selectively etch and recess the exposed Mo beneath the CIGS precursor (Figure 2A-6). This creates a small lateral undercut in the back contact. The CIGS precursor was crystallized in Se-containing atmosphere at 460°C in a horizontal split-tube (Thermolab) with the samples placed inside a graphite box, under atmospheric pressure and an argon flow of 100 sccm (Figure 2-7). A $\sim 50 \text{ nm}$ CdS buffer layer was grown by chemical bath deposition (CBD) at 60°C for 14 min using a precursor solution consisting of cadmium acetate ($3.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) (Cd source), thiourea ($1.3 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$) (S source), and ammonium hydroxide (1.7 M) (complexing agent) (Figure 2A-8). The solar cell stack was completed with a transparent top contact deposited by RF sputtering in the STAR system [18], consisting of 20 nm (Zn, Mg)O (Testbourne, 50 W, 6.2×10^{-3} mbar) and 200 nm ZnO:Al (Testbourne, 60 W, 5.2×10^{-3} mbar), as shown in Figure 2A-8. (More details can be found in the Supporting Information S3).

2.1.2 | LOR Bi-Layer Route

The LOR-based bottom-up process (Figure 2B) followed the same sequence as the bleach-etch approach, but the SLG substrates were first coated with a 0.8 μm lift-off resist (LOR) layer beneath

the 2.2 μm PR film (Figure 2B-2,3). This bi-layer configuration creates a controlled undercut during development, resulting in a tapered film profile after Mo/a-CIGS deposition (Figure 2B-4,5). The lift-off was performed by immersing the samples at 60°C in a dedicated PR remover (Mr-REM 500) for 30 min without

ultrasonic agitation, followed by 30 min with ultrasonic treatment (Figure 2B-6).

2.2 | Top-Down Fabrication of an STPV Mini-Module

We used 10 \times 10 cm^2 complete opaque CIGS solar mini-modules fabricated at the Center for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research Baden-Württemberg (ZSW) (stack: SLG/Mo/CIGS/CdS/i-ZnO/ZnO:Al) with monolithic P1, P2, and P3 interconnection, and micro-structured them into a semitransparent mini-module following the sequence in Figure 3. The CIGS absorber was deposited with an in-line multi-stage co-evaporation process, the aperture area efficiency of the mini-module was 14.0% [19]. The best reference cell on the same carrier exhibits a total area efficiency of 18.4% (without anti-reflective coating), $V_{\text{OC}} = 721$ mV, $FF = 77.6\%$, and $J_{\text{SC}} = 32.8$ mA cm^{-2} . We patterned the substrate, perpendicularly to the P1-P3 interconnection, to define a 2.92 \times 2.35 cm^2 segmented aperture containing five series-connected cells and 36 parallel micro-stripes, each 2.35 cm long with 400 μm width and 400 μm spacing.

To realise the pattern, a 2.2 μm PR layer was spin-coated onto the completed device (Figure 3-2), patterned into micro-lines with the

FIGURE 3 | Schematic illustration of the top-down segmentation process for micro-striped CIGS solar cells (cross-section). A single micro-line is shown for clarity: (1) completed CIGS device; (2) PR deposition; (3) PR exposure and development; (4) etching of window and buffer layers; (5) etching of the CIGS layer; (6) etching of the Mo back contact; (7) PR removal.

FIGURE 4 | Cross-sectional SEM micrograph comparison of the reference, bleach, and LOR micro-stripping routes: (A) Unmitigated reference structure showing continuous Mo/CIGS sidewall deposition along the PR walls. These “ears” remain exposed after crystallization and create direct shunt pathways once the window layer is deposited. (B) Bleach route. (C) LOR route. Together, these cross-sections show how the bleach and LOR routes eliminate the sidewall continuity present in the reference process, addressing the identified shunting mechanism.

FIGURE 5 | Micro-striped CIGS test structures and representative J - V curves for different stripe widths. (A) Optical images of micro-striped test devices comprising parallel CIGS lines with widths of 200, 300, 500, and 1000 μm ; (B) Representative J - V curves for stripes of different widths fabricated using the bleach (dashed lines) and LOR (solid lines) variants. Across all geometries, LOR stripes show higher J_{sc} and FF , demonstrating the superior suppression of sidewall-related shunting relative to the bleach approach.

DWL, and developed (Figure 3–3). The exposed window and buffer layers were removed in 10% HCl (Figure 3–4). The CIGS was etched using an aqueous bromine solution (details can be found in P. Santos et al. [17]) (Figure 3–5). Subsequently, the Mo back-contact was etched with bleach for 30 s (Figure 3–6). Finally, the PR was removed in acetone and the sample rinsed with IPA and DI water (Figure 3–7). (More details can be found in the Supporting Information S3).

2.3 | Characterisation Methods

The micro-stripped devices were characterised by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta) equipped with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The mini-module optical transmittance spectra were recorded with a PerkinElmer LAMBDA

950 UV–VIS–NIR spectrophotometer to determine the CRI and AVT following the procedure in C. Yang et al. [14].

For electrical measurements of the bottom-up test structures, individual CIGS micro-strips were isolated by mechanically scribing the window layer between adjacent lines. For each individual micro-stripe, contacts were established using a four-point probe measurement configuration: two probes were positioned on the shared Mo back-contact bus bar, which was covered with indium to ensure a low-resistance connection, and the remaining two probes were placed directly on the ZnO:Al top contact.

For the mini-module, the segmented aperture was isolated by removing the surrounding unpatterned regions, and the device was contacted using two probes on the ZnO:Al pad connecting to the Mo back-contact of the first cell and two on the Mo pad

FIGURE 6 | Electrical impact of stripe width and sidewall-mitigation strategy on micro-stripped CIGS cells. Boxplots summarising the photovoltaic parameters of micro-strips fabricated by the bleach (blue) and LOR (green) approaches for stripe widths of 200–1000 μm. Panels show: (A) PCE, (B) V_{oc} , (C) J_{sc} , (D) FF, (E) series resistance (R_s), and (F) shunt resistance (R_{sh}).

extended from the ZnO:Al top-contact of the fifth cell, enabling the five series-connected cells to be measured as a single string. Current density–voltage (J - V) measurements were carried out under AM1.5 illumination (100 mW cm^{-2}) using a halogen lamp calibrated with a Si reference cell and a class-AAA solar simulator (Oriel Sol3A).

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Morphology of the Micro-Striped CIGS Solar Cells

As mentioned in the Introduction, sputtering onto vertical PR trenches leads to continuous Mo and CIGS deposition along the resist walls, producing ‘ears’. These continuous sidewall features provide a direct pathway for shunting once the window layer is deposited. The reference cross-section in Figure 4A represents this unmitigated case, where indeed the Mo layer curls up and around the top of the CIGS micro-stripe. To mitigate this, the following strategies were tried, namely, Mo under-etching and LOR-induced resist undercut.

In the bleach route, the Mo under-etch produces a lateral $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ recess beneath the CIGS (Figure 4B) that breaks the continuity of

the material accumulated along the resist walls during sputtering, interrupting possible conductive bridges to the top contact. In contrast, the LOR process yields a tapered film profile after deposition (Figure 4C), reducing vertical sidewall accumulation and enabling the CIGS to grow continuously over the Mo. Although the geometries differ, both strategies eliminate the resist wall effect and produce well-defined absorber stripes.

3.2 | Performance of Micro-Striped CIGS Cells

To probe how segmentation affects device behaviour, we measured individual micro-strips with widths ranging from 200 to $1000 \mu\text{m}$ patterned in parallel on the same substrate. This geometry isolates the impact of stripe width and sidewall-mitigation strategy on series resistance, shunting, and overall photovoltaic performance. Figure 5 shows a representative device where the designed stripe geometry areas were used to calculate PCE and J_{sc} . The LOR route consistently delivers higher efficiencies than the bleach route for all stripe widths, with the best devices around 3%–4% efficiency at $500 \mu\text{m}$. Bleach-processed stripes exhibit lower average efficiencies and show broader device-to-device variability.

The boxplots in Figure 6 condense these trends. Micro-striped CIGS solar cells fabricated by the LOR route exhibit higher open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), J_{sc} , and fill factor (FF) on average, together

FIGURE 7 | Semi-transparent CIGS mini-module demonstrating scalable spatial segmentation with preserved optical and electrical functionality. (A) Patterned $2.92 \times 2.35 \text{ cm}^2$ striped aperture spanning five series-connected cells in the centre of a $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ monolithically interconnected CIGS module. The blue and yellow regions denote the extended back-contact (cell 1) and extended top-contact (cell 5) pads, respectively; these lie outside the active window and are used only for probing; (B) Optical transmittance spectra of the mini-module and a soda-lime glass reference (solid lines) together with the photopic response of the human eye (dashed line); (C) J - V curve of the five-cell series-interconnected mini-module.

TABLE 1 | Electrical performance metrics comparison between the STPV mini-module and the non-patterned reference device.

Sample	Active Area PCE, %	Total Area PCE, %	Active Area J_{sc} , mA cm^{-2}	V_{oc} , V	FF , %	R_{s} , $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	R_{sh} , $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$
Reference	13.0	13.0	5.54	3.32	68.2	90.4	16245.2
STPV	10.9	5.45	4.60	3.35	68.1	106.9	24162.2

with narrower parameter distributions, indicating a more reliable fabrication process. In contrast, CIGS micro-stripes from the bleach route show wide scatter, consistent with the more sensitive and less controllable Mo under-etch. Across both approaches, V_{oc} and J_{sc} increase moderately with stripe width, reflecting reduced series resistance and weaker edge effects in wider lines.

The differences between the two routes appear most clearly in R_s and R_{sh} . The LOR route leads to devices with lower and more stable series resistance, and systematically higher shunt resistance, indicating fewer leakage paths. Micro-stripes from the bleach route show a larger spread in R_s , which may indicate occasional residual partially etched Mo or local defects at the line edges (see Supporting Information, Figure S5).

3.3 | Demonstration of a Semi-Transparent CIGS Mini-Module

To assess the scalability of spatial segmentation, we evaluated a semi-transparent mini-module fabricated by the top-down route. The device operates as a five-cell series string within a segmented aperture and presents as a uniform striped window, with a few darker regions caused by residual Mo (Figure 7A). Optical transmission measurements show an AVT of about 40%, compared to about 92% for bare glass (Figure 7B). The spectrum is colour-neutral, with a colour rendering index of 98.9, which is appropriate for STPV window applications [14].

Table 1 quantifies the main electrical trade-offs introduced by segmentation. The interconnected mini-module delivers 5.45% total-area efficiency and 10.9% active-area efficiency (Figure 7C). This value represents a 16% relative decrease in comparison with the 13.0% efficiency of the reference measurement performed on a non-patterned region of the same module (Table 1) (see Supporting Information S4 for more details). The difference in active-area PCE results from the J_{sc} deterioration from 5.54 mA cm⁻² on the reference to 4.6 mA cm⁻² on the STPV module, while V_{oc} and FF are consistent with reference values. This current loss can be partially justified by the stripe edges' dead area generated during the top-down patterning fabrication process. As shown in P. Santos et al. [17], the chemical etching process produces over 20 μm over-etching of the window layer on each side of the stripes, representing losses > 10% in the total active area of the device. Furthermore, the STPV module exhibits a slightly higher series resistance compared to the reference (107 vs. 90 Ω cm²), which can indicate some hindrance of the top transparent conducting oxide (TCO). At the same time, the shunt resistance also increases, suggesting that no major leakage paths were introduced with the patterning fabrication process. With an AVT of 40.6% and a PCE_{total area} of 5.45%, the STPV mini-module delivers a light-utilisation efficiency (LUE) of 2.2%. Among reported spatially segmented CIGS devices, this value lies at the upper end of published LUE performance [20].

4 | Conclusions

Spatial segmentation provides a simple route to semi-transparent CIGS based energy generating windows that preserves full absorber performance. By segmenting the absorber material into sub-visual micro-stripes, we achieve colour-neutral transmission while maintaining the local photovoltaic quality of full-thickness

CIGS. With a bottom-up process we can create micro-stripes with a simple Mo under-etch, though this approach requires further optimisation, while the LOR-defined undercut already provides reliable pattern transfer. The top-down implementation confirms that segmented stripes can be interconnected into an efficient five-cell mini-module. At 40% AVT and 5.45% total-area efficiency, the mini-module reaches a light-utilisation efficiency of 2.2%, demonstrating that segmentation can scale to device-relevant areas without compromising optical neutrality or electrical operation. Spatial segmentation therefore, offers a viable architecture for integrating high-efficiency and aesthetically pleasing photovoltaics into building windows.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Orlando Oliveira from the Kolen'ko Group at INL for chemistry guidance, especially on the preparation and neutralisation of the bromine etching solution. The authors acknowledge support by the project "Semi-TranspARent SOLar cells for building integrated photovoltaics (STAR-SOL)", funded by FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT-FNR/0001/2018) and the Fond National de la Recherche (C18/MS/12686759). This research was partly funded by the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) under the 2022 Joint Call for research proposals, co-funded by the European Commission (GA no. 101069750) and by Portuguese National Funds from FCT- Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, under the project "TRANSMIT - Semi-transparent micro-striped photovoltaics for energy harvesting windows" (CETP/0008/2022). The research was partially funded by the European Union under the project "Hi-BITS - High efficiency bifacial thin film chalcogenide solar cells" (Grant Agreement no. 101122203). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Open access publication funding provided by FCT (b-on).

Funding

This study was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Grant FCT-FNR/0001/2018 and CETP/0008/2022), and European Commission (Grant 101122203).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. C. J. Traverse, R. Pandey, M. C. Barr, and R. R. Lunt, "Emergence of Highly Transparent Photovoltaics for Distributed Applications," *Nature Energy* 2, no. 11 (2017): 849–860, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-017-0016-9>.
2. W. Zhang, L. Lu, J. Peng, and A. Song, "Comparison of the Overall Energy Performance of Semi-Transparent Photovoltaic Windows and Common Energy-Efficient Windows in Hong Kong," *Energy and Buildings* 128 (2016): 511–518, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.07.016>.
3. Y. Sun, K. Shanks, H. Baig, et al., "Integrated Semi-Transparent Cadmium Telluride Photovoltaic Glazing into Windows: Energy and Daylight Performance for Different Architecture Designs," *Applied Energy* 231 (2018): 972–984, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.09.133>.

4. S. H. Moon, S. J. Park, Y. J. Hwang, et al., “Printable, Wide Band-Gap Chalcopyrite Thin Films for Power Generating Window Applications,” *Scientific Reports* 4, no. 1 (2014): 4408, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep04408>.
5. I. Massiot, A. Cattoni, and S. Collin, “Progress and Prospects for Ultrathin Solar Cells,” *Nature Energy* 5, no. 12 (2020): 959–972, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-00714-4>.
6. O. Lundberg, M. Bodegård, J. Malmström, and L. Stolt, “Influence of the Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thickness and Ga Grading on Solar Cell Performance,” *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications* 11, no. 2 (2003): 77–88, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.462>.
7. M. J. Shin, J. H. Jo, A. Cho, et al., “Semi-Transparent Photovoltaics Using Ultra-Thin Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Absorber Layers Prepared by Single-Stage Co-Evaporation,” *Solar Energy* 181 (2019): 276–284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.02.003>.
8. K. Kim and W. N. Shafarman, “Alternative Device Structures for CIGS-Based Solar Cells with Semi-Transparent Absorbers,” *Nano Energy* 30 (2016): 488–493, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2016.10.038>.
9. M. J. Shin, S. Park, A. Lee, et al., “Bifacial Photovoltaic Performance of Semitransparent Ultrathin Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells with Front and Rear Transparent Conducting Oxide Contacts,” *Applied Surface Science* 535 (2021): 147732, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.147732>.
10. D. Kim, S. S. Shin, S. M. Lee, et al., “Flexible and Semi-Transparent Ultra-Thin CIGSe Solar Cells Prepared on Ultra-Thin Glass Substrate: A Key to Flexible Bifacial Photovoltaic Applications,” *Advanced Functional Materials* 30, no. 36 (2020):2001775, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202001775>.
11. D. Kim, S. S. Shin, Y. Jo, et al., “Practical Enhancements in Current Density and Power Generation of Bifacial Semitransparent Ultrathin CIGSe Solar Cells via Utilization of Wide Bandgap Zn-Based Buffer,” *Advancement of Science* 9, no. 13 (2022): 2105436, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202105436>.
12. M. Saifullah, S. J. Ahn, J. Gwak, et al., “Development of Semitransparent CIGS Thin-Film Solar Cells Modified with a Sulfurized-AgGa Layer for Building Applications,” *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 4, no. 27 (2016): 10542–10551, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6TA01909A>.
13. A. Jeong, J. M. Choi, H.-J. Lee, et al., “Transparent Back-Junction Control in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Absorber for High-Efficiency, Color-Neutral, and Semitransparent Solar Module,” *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications* 30, no. 7 (2022): 713–725, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.3520>.
14. C. Yang, D. Liu, M. Bates, M. C. Barr, and R. R. Lunt, “How to Accurately Report Transparent Solar Cells,” *Joule* 3, no. 8 (2019): 1803–1809, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2019.06.005>.
15. I. H. Warren and D. M. Mounsey, “Factors Influencing the Selective Leaching of Molybdenum with Sodium Hypochlorite from Copper/Molybdenum Sulphide Minerals,” *Hydrometallurgy* 10, no. 3 (1983): 343–357, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-386X\(83\)90064-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-386X(83)90064-6).
16. Y. Chen, “A Lift-Off Process for High Resolution Patterns Using PMMA / LOR Resist Stack,” *Microelectronic Engineering* 73-74 (2004): 278–281, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mee.2004.02.053>.
17. P. Santos, P. Anacleto, D. Brito, et al., “Fabrication of Semi-Transparent Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells Aided by Bromine Etching,” *Thin Solid Films* 770 (2023): 139778, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2023.139778>.
18. D. Fuster, P. Anacleto, J. Virtuoso, “System for Manufacturing Complete Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells In Situ under Vacuum,” *Solar Energy* 198 (2020): 490–498, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.01.073>.
19. R. Gutzler, W. Witte, A. Kanevce, D. Hariskos, and S. Paetel, “VOC-Losses across the Band Gap: Insights from a High-Throughput Inline Process for CIGS Solar Cells,” *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications* 31, no. 10 (2023): 1023–1031, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.3707>.
20. C. Xu, Y. Chen, Z. Zhao, et al., “Semi-Transparent Photovoltaics,” *Energy & Environmental Science* 18, no. 5 (2025), 2095–2135, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4ee04209c>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.